

DI Model for Imitation False Face, Age, Gender and Scenario Disparities

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ABSTRACT

Scrutinises many methods that are employed by numerous scholars to identify Deep phoney films. We offer a method for spotting identity changes, such face swapping, in a single photograph. Deep Fake and other facial swapping methods alter the face region in an effort to replicate the appearance of the context while changing only the face. We show that the two regions differ as a result of this mode of operation. These variations raise red flags for manipulative activity. Our method makes use of a pair of networks: one for face identification, that takes into account face region included within accurate semantic segmentation & specifies gender and age, and another for context recognition, which takes into account face's surrounding context. Recognizing the Meaning of Emoticons, we provide a strategy which makes use of recognition signals from our 2 networks to pinpoint these deviations, so offering an enhanced, non-traditional detection signal. We propose a deep fake-detection method based on an organ-level transformer model for extracting deep fake characteristics. By giving less weight to identification of deformed or unclear organs, we give priority to detection of obvious and intact organs. Our system can also detect subtle alterations to facial expressions and details, as well as heavily tainted, digitally-generated phony images. So-called "micro expressions" are fast, fleeting facial changes. This kind of unrestrained display of emotion is a window into a person's true feelings. examined the seven most common micro expressions seen in human faces: happiness, sadness, anger, disgust, contempt, fear, & surprise.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Many people believe that photography provides reliable proof of actual events, particularly the appearance and behaviour of people in pictures and movies. Even though this impression is steadily changing, modern technology makes picture alteration far simpler and more accessible than most people realise. Every time distorted media is disseminated through social networks and ingested by a populace that lacks the skills to verify its veracity, this gap poses a threat to society. For instance, today's actors may more easily imitate another person by speaking a script whilst using voice & face manipulation software. Alternately, it is possible to alter and swap out a person's captured face from a crime scene. Face switching is the term used to describe both of these instances. Third, acting out someone else face to change their emotion or lip movement is detailed. Modern techniques for identifying these modifications

approach all 3 cases in similar fashion: by training classifier to tell difference amongst real and fake photos or videos. However, that the third situation is distinct from the first two in that an identity shift is not involved. Our objective is to record the cues produced by face swapping, which alters the apparent identity, when it occurs. Due to the fact that many of the modern face alteration techniques were developed for use cases where identities were changed, figure 1 shows the swapping technique. In order to achieve this, we assume two things: (A1) Facial modification techniques only modify the interior of face. (A2) Outside of internal region of face, head, neck, teeth, nose, & hair sections all provide a significant distinguishing signal to individual. The gender and age are also being determined by researchers. The characteristics of a person's face can be used to determine their identity, age, and gender. Gender Prediction is presented as a classification issue. The gender prediction

network's output layer has two nodes representing the classes "Male" and "Female" and is of the softmax kind. Since we anticipate a real number as the output, age forecast must be handled like an regression problem. Accurate age estimation using regression is challenging. The Audience information is broken down into 8 categories based on age ranges (0-2), 3-6, 6-12, 15-20, 25-32, 38-43, 48-53, 60-100). Age prediction network uses softmax layer with 8 nodes to represent the aforementioned age brackets. By using Haar Cascade to determine the location of inner face area, we propose unique signal for detecting manipulated photos. Picture size and position of item being sought are both irrelevant to effectiveness of Haar cascade technique for object detection. Since it is not too complicated, this method can function in real time, the modified one - and its external environment, which is unaffected by known face alteration techniques.

Figure 1: Deep Fake faces

II. RELATED WORK

Deep Fake is generative deep learning system that generates or modifies[1] facial characteristics in such a way as it's almost impossible to tell them apart from the actual thing.

We give a literature review and an evaluation [5] of detection capabilities of various approaches in relation to various data sets, with the conclusion that deep learning-based methods are superior than others in detection of Deep fakes.

With use of deep fakes and techniques like generative adversarial networks, video material may be automatically generated [9] & created.

Presented a novel strategy for revealing neural network-generated false face videos [15]. The approach depends upon identification of eye blinking in videos, physiological signal which is poorly represented in phony films created via the synthesis process.

Presented a novel deep learning based approach that can accurately distinguish actual films from those made by artificial intelligence [26]

It is challenging for human eyes to tell the difference between a computer-generated (CG) picture [27] & natural image (NI). In this paper, we address these basic picture forensics issue by proposing a solution based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

Absence of sufficient datasets has severely impeded research into detection of facial modifications [28]. Considering movies compressed at different quality levels, we provide benchmarks for traditional image forensic tasks such as classification & segmentation.

Recurrent convolutional networks [29] are a kind of deep learning models that demonstrate success in using temporal information in picture streams in variety of applications.

Using provided data set, primary focus of this study is to identify subjects' ages & genders [35]. Python & Keras were utilized for their relative ease in determining a person's age and gender.

To accomplish accurate age and gender categorization of real-world faces, we suggest a revolutionary [36] end-to-end CNN technique.

Research on video-based micro-expression analysis follows a cascading structure, beginning with a discussion of the differences between macro- and micro-expressions [37] and moving on to a look at the neuropsychological foundation, datasets, applications etc.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our method uses a pair of networks: (i) face recognition network which looks at area around face defined by a strict semantic segmentation, & (ii) context recognition network which takes into account surrounding facial features. Using recognition signals from our pair of networks, we detail a technique for identifying these deviations, thereby enhancing the performance of standard genuine versus fake classifiers in the process. Our approach generalizes to identify fakes made using unknown techniques, and it obtains state-of-art results utilizing Face Forensics++ & Celeb-DF-v2 benchmarks for face modification detection. The software can determine a user's age and gender. SVM categorizes people into two sex categories (male and female) and eight age categories. Talking about the nuances of facial expression.

Figure 2. Micro Expressions

Figure 2 shows some of the micro expression such as sadly disgusted, happily surprised, sadly angry, angrily disgusted. Recognizing micro-expressions might help DoD forensics & intelligence mission capability by offering clues to foresee & intercept potentially harmful situations since they can disclose emotions someone might be attempting to conceal.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We're utilizing 50 photos from various sources for our own Deep fake dataset. Our data collection is composed of train dataset (70%) and a test dataset (30%).

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During preprocessing, movies are first divided in 10 frames, then face detection is performed, the identified frame is cropped, & new face cropped dataset is generated. Throughout preprocessing phase, we will disregard remaining frames. Figure 3 depicts pre-processing phase's workflow.

Figure 3 Pre-processing

Resize image: Each photograph in data set were different sizes, & processing data of different sizes wasn't able to produce an appropriate result. All of photos were downscaled to 256 by 256 pixels before being processed further. Input picture was resized using down sampling & upsampling techniques.

Noise reduction: Raw input face picture has its noise eliminated through Kalman filter so that categorization of deep fake images would be more accurate.

Prediction Process

Priori estimate is premeditated in prediction procedure by utilising

$$X_n = T_n X_{n-1} \quad (1)$$

Covariance matrix is deliberated by Eqn

$$C_n = T_n P_{n-1} T_n^T + PPN_n \quad (2)$$

Update Procedure

Kalman Gain matrix is given as

$$\text{Eqn } KG_n = P_n O_n^t \cdot (O_n^t P_n O_n^t + CUN_n)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Posteriori estimate is done by

$$\text{Eqn } Z_n: X_n = X_n + KG_n (Z_n - O_n X_n) \quad (4)$$

Posteriori estimate covariance matrix is deliberated as

$$\text{Eqn } P_n^1 = (I - KG_n \cdot O_n) \cdot P_n \quad (5)$$

Kalman filter parameters must be fine-tuned using covariance matrices of noises like PPN, OUN, and P+0. The predicted weights are based on such covariance matrices. Its filter's background noise follows multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean zero & variance one. Equation 1 is a representation of covariance matrix of sample vector $X = [X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n]^T$.

$$\Sigma \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1} & \dots & \sum_{i=n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_{n,1} & \dots & \sum_{n,m} \end{bmatrix}$$

here $\sum_{i,j} \text{cov}(X_i, X_j) = E[(X_i - \eta_i)(X_j - \eta_j)] = E[X_i X_j]$, & E is expectation operator. Both dynamic and static approaches are used to address filter adjustment. Using methods like ALS, static

tuning fine-tunes filter before it is used. In addition when filter is self-tuning, dynamic tuning fine-tunes it. Additionally, it employs a technique known as Artificial Neural Network. For purpose of choosing most important features for classification, the pre-processed data from Kalman filter are sent into feature selection stage.

MODEL: A resnext50 32x4d & LSTM layer make up model. Data Loader takes in face-cropped films that have already been processed and sorts them in training and test sets. After the films have been analyzed, individual frames are sent to model for both training and assessment. ResNeXt design is very similar to ResNet's, with addition of fourth dimension known as Cardinality.

Fig-4: RESNext

In figure4 ResNext, on left, & ResNeXt, on right, are both convolutional neural networks that use split-transform-merge design. This method uses a 1x1 convolutional layer to reduce dimensionality of input before applying a 3x3 or 5x5 special filter and summing results back together. The gathered transformations are all from same topology, therefore they may be used with little to no requirement for custom implementations. ResNeXt's primary goal is to process massive inputs while enhancing network accuracy without resorting to deeper layer construction, instead opting to do it through an increase in cardinality that keeps complexity low.

Simple neuron

Figure5: Simple Neuron

In neural networks, the simplest neurons function as shown in figure 5. In Simple Neuron Inputs $[x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_D]$ are changed by weights $[w_1, w_2, \dots, w_D]$, followed by summed utilizing aggregation function.

ResNeXt will use the same idea, albeit it will employ a more generalized function for processing input rather than just concatenating weights.

$$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^c T_i(x)$$

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Input variable "x," where "C" is the network's cardinality and "Ti(x)" is the generic function that we've been discussing.

Fig-6: ResNeXt architecture

Figure 6 shows that (a) is comparable to (b) & (c) (Inception Resnet and Grouped Convolution, respectively).

In contrast to (a), convolutions in (b) are clustered in (c), and early concatenation is a feature of (c).

Extraction of features with resnext50

Features are being extracted using resnext50, and their frame level detection accuracy is also improved. Tuning cnn network involves adding layers and choosing learning rate that allows gradient to be converged upon. After last pooling layers, sequential LSTM shall be fed 2048-dimensional feature vectors.

LSTM is made up of 3 Gates:

- 1) Input Gate.
- 2) Forget Gate.
- 3) Output Gate.

Successfully determined person's gender and age using only a single facial picture using Deep Learning. Its anticipated gender could be either "Male" or "Female," & expected age can fall anywhere from 0 to 2 years old to 8 decades old (with 8 nodes in final soft max layer).

Figure 7: Finding Age and Gender

Pseudo code for Age Estimation

- Initialize w by random values

- Generate candidate aging pattern vector
- Minimize by w with respect to condition $0 \leq w_i \leq 1$
- Age of test face may be deduced from location of largest element in optimal w.

V. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 8: System Architecture

In Figure 8 architecture, proposed a novel deepfake-detection architecture. Firstly, we extracted organs, like eyes, ears etc, and we built the transformer encoder and calculated the feature vector. In addition to standard methods of gender and age discrimination, a whole-face transducer encoder was developed. Then, we formed a feature-vector group by combining vectors representing every part of body as well as whole face. At long last, the vector set has been categorized. Feature weights had been initialized to zero before organ was dyed.

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Two networks were used in prior research: (i) face identification network, which takes into account face area within the bounds of a strict semantic segmentation, & (ii) context recognition network, which takes into account face's surroundings. There has been a decline in precision of phrase. So we implemented the facial expression such as joy, sorrow, rage, disgust, contempt, fear, and surprise. With age prediction is discussed with face identification and context recognition using Haar cascade e.g. ears, neck, teeth, nose, eyebrows, eyes, and mouth whether fake or real.

VII. CONCLUSION

We present a deepfake-detection approach for face features that can accurately identify false media. All except the most egregious cases of expression-manipulation, incomplete detail-modification, & tainted deepfake photos may be easily detected by our approach. To get the characteristics, we also construct transformers on an organ level. Reduced weights of discolored, deformed, or otherwise subpar organs helped improve precision. To aid in identification of incomplete data, whole-face rectifier was also used. We also created test data set, FOFDTD, to mimic real-world circumstances for fake content facial organ detection. Mask face, sunglasses face, & bare face make up dataset. It

Figure 9: Read Image

Figure 10: Gray Scale Image

Figure 11: Denoise Image

Male (15-20)

Figure 12: Age and gender Detection

Figure 13: Fake Detection

detects micro expressions such as sad, anger, happy of face, and also detects gender. In Future detecting macro expressions as well discussing regarding difference between micro and macro expressions.

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